

Ultrasound Findings of the Knee and Their Relationship with Pain in Patients Aged 30 to 60 Years at HGR 1 in Orizaba, Veracruz

Montes-Osorio MG¹, Hernández-Rivera JC^{2*}, Vera-Hernández FA³, De Dios-Gómez E⁴

¹Specialist in Nuclear Medicine, Coordination of Planning and Institutional Liaison, Orizaba, Veracruz, Mexico

²Specialist in Nephrology, CMN SXXI Specialty Hospital, Mexico City, Mexico

³Specialist in Radiology and Imaging, Regional General Hospital No. 1 “Ignacio García Téllez”, Orizaba, Veracruz, Mexico

⁴Resident in Diagnostic and Therapeutic Imaging, Faculty of Medicine, Universidad Veracruzana, Orizaba, Veracruz, Mexico

ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Background: Knee pathology is common and affects quality of life. The most frequent lesions are synovitis, bursitis, trochlear cartilage damage, and tendinopathies, with cartilage wear being relevant due to its relationship with mechanical overload. Early detection is key, and ultrasound, due to its accessibility, allows identification of the etiological cause of pain.

Objective: To determine knee ultrasound findings associated with pain in patients aged 30–60 years at HGR 1 Orizaba, Veracruz.

Material and Methods: Descriptive, cross-sectional study in beneficiaries aged 30–60 years, with and without knee pain. Philips ultrasound was applied with a high-frequency linear transducer (7.5–12 MHz), evaluating synovitis, bursitis, tendinitis, meniscal lesions, soft tissue inflammation, and cartilage changes. Pain intensity was measured with VAS (0–10). Sociodemographic and clinical data were collected (age, sex, BMI, diabetes, physical activity). Descriptive and inferential statistics were used (Chi-square). Period: August–December 2025.

Results: The most frequent findings were cartilage changes (49%) and bursitis (44%), followed by tendinitis, meniscal lesions, and synovitis. In patients with pain, prevalence was higher: bursitis (84.4%), cartilage (80%), tendinitis (39%), meniscal lesions (37.9%), and synovitis (12.3%). Bilateral pain predominated (78.3%). Intensity showed a dose–response relationship: higher VAS was associated with more findings. Older age and obesity increased risk, while sex and diabetes were not significant. Mild physical activity predominated (62%) and was associated with more pain; vigorous activity showed a protective effect. Sports practice and active work were associated with lower prevalence of findings.

Conclusions: Knee pain in adults is associated with ultrasound findings, mainly cartilage changes and bursitis. A dose–response relationship between VAS and structural damage was confirmed, with elevated risks for tendinitis and meniscal lesions. Age and obesity were determining factors, while vigorous and moderate physical activity showed a protective effect. Ultrasound is reaffirmed as a useful diagnostic tool and exercise as a preventive strategy to reduce musculoskeletal load.

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KEYWORDS: Ultrasound findings, knee pain, synovitis, bursitis, tendinitis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background: Knee pathology constitutes a relevant clinical problem due to its high prevalence across diverse populations, including athletes, older individuals, and those with risk factors such as obesity and diabetes mellitus. Among the alterations observed, trochlear cartilage lesions,

tendinous injuries, bursitis, and synovitis stand out, each with particular epidemiological characteristics that have been the subject of recent literature. Regarding cartilage lesions, different studies have reported a prevalence ranging from 15% to 30% in patients with patellofemoral pain, with

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particular incidence in the trochlear cartilage, where wear is associated with repetitive use and mechanical overload.

This situation is of particular importance in degenerative pathology, in which early detection may favor the implementation of preventive or therapeutic strategies. Regarding tendinous lesions, prevalence varies considerably depending on the segment evaluated and the patient's activity level. Studies in active populations and athletes indicate that tendinous alterations in the knee (for example, patellar tendinopathy) range between 10% and 25%, while in less active groups this figure may be lower, although it still represents a frequent cause of pain and functional limitation.

The etiology of osteoarthritis includes predisposing factors such as advanced age, overweight, and family history of joint diseases. Excess weight significantly increases the load on the joints, thereby accelerating cartilage wear. In addition, repetitive activities or previous knee injuries may contribute to the premature development of this degenerative condition. It is important to highlight that certain sports or occupations requiring intense joint movements may increase risk due to the constant mechanical stress applied to the joints.

With the objective of determining knee ultrasound findings associated with pain in patients aged 30–60 years treated at HGR No. 1 Orizaba, Veracruz.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design: Descriptive, cross-sectional study.

Period: August 1 to December 31, 2025.

Institution: HGR No. 1 of the Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS).

Ethical aspects: Approved by the Local Ethics and Research Committee No. 3101. Institutional registration: R-2025-3101-068.

Population and sample: Patients aged 30–60 years, beneficiaries with and without knee pain, who met inclusion criteria, were invited to participate. The final sample consisted of 208 patients.

Procedure:

- A structured questionnaire was applied to collect sociodemographic data (age, sex, body mass index, physical activity), history of knee pain, and relevant comorbidities.
- Subsequently, knee ultrasound was performed using Philips equipment with a high-frequency linear transducer (7.5–12 MHz). Synovitis, bursitis, tendinitis, meniscal lesions, soft tissue inflammation, and cartilage changes were evaluated.
- Pain intensity was measured using the visual analog scale (VAS, 0–10).
- Two radiologists verified each procedure to ensure quality control.

Sampling: A data collection instrument and knee ultrasound were used to assess structural alterations.

Statistical analysis:

- Univariate analysis was performed for demographic variables.
- Quantitative variables: expressed as median and ranges, or mean \pm standard deviation (SD).
- Qualitative variables: presented as frequencies and percentages.
- Chi-square test was used for categorical variables.
- Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.
- Software: IBM SPSS version 24

III. RESULTS

A. Sociodemographic characteristics

The study included 208 patients, analyzing a total of 416 knees. The median age was 47 years (IQR 38–54), with a median weight of 70 kg (IQR 62–80), height of 1.60 m (IQR 1.56–1.73), and a body mass index (BMI) of 25.8 kg/m² (IQR 25.3–27.8). Pain perception measured by the visual analog scale (VAS) showed a median of 3 points (IQR 0–7). Regarding sex, 61.1% were women and 38.9% men. The prevalence of diabetes mellitus was 8.7%. With respect to physical activity, mild activity predominated (62%), followed by moderate (17.8%), none (15.4%), and vigorous (4.8%). A total of 29.8% practiced some sport, and 82.7% were occupationally active.

B. Ultrasound findings related to knee pain

A total of 44.2% reported pain in both knees, 23.8% in one knee, and 32% reported no pain. When categorizing pain intensity using VAS, 43.5% reported no pain, 12% reported mild pain, 32% moderate pain, and 12.5% severe pain. The most frequent ultrasound findings were cartilage changes (49.5%) and bursitis (47.8%), followed by tendinitis (22.4%), meniscal lesions (21.4%), and synovitis (7%).

When comparing patients with and without pain, those with pain were older (52 vs 38 years, $p=0.001$), had higher weight (71 vs 68 kg, $p=0.006$), and higher BMI (26.0 vs 25.6 kg/m², $p=0.001$). VAS scores were significantly higher in the pain group (5 points vs 0, $p=0.001$). No differences were found in sex or diabetes. However, vigorous and moderate physical activity were more frequent in patients without pain, while mild or no activity predominated in those with pain ($p=0.001$). Similarly, sports practice was more common in the group without pain (50.8% vs 13.6%, $p=0.001$), and the proportion of occupationally active patients was higher among those without pain (96.1% vs 72.3%, $p=0.001$).

In the analysis of clinical and ultrasound findings, patients with pain reported predominantly bilateral involvement (78.3%), while in the group without pain most showed no involvement (73.5%, $p=0.001$). When categorizing pain intensity, all patients without pain were classified as “no

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pain,” while in the pain group moderate pain predominated (56.6%), followed by mild (21.3%) and severe (22.1%, $p=0.001$). The ultrasound findings significantly more frequent in patients with pain were: cartilage changes (80% vs 9.9%), bursitis (84.3% vs 0.6%), tendinitis (39.1% vs 0.6%), meniscal lesions (37.9% vs 0%), and synovitis (12.3% vs 0%), all with $p=0.001$.

C. Analysis by pain intensity

When analyzing ultrasound findings in relation to pain intensity, a dose–response pattern was evident. Cartilage changes were observed in 9.9% of patients without pain, increasing to 48% in mild pain, 85.7% in moderate pain, and 96.2% in severe pain. Bursitis was practically absent in the group without pain (0.6%), but progressively increased to reach 100% in severe pain. Synovitis showed a similar pattern, absent in the group without pain and increasing from 2% in mild pain to 36.5% in severe pain. Tendinitis was identified in only 0.6% of patients without pain, while its frequency was 10% in mild pain, 31.6% in moderate pain, and 86.5% in severe pain. Meniscal lesions were also associated with greater pain intensity, increasing from 0% in the group without pain to 4% in mild pain, 30.1% in moderate pain, and 90.4% in severe pain. In the analysis by specific VAS scores (2–9), the prevalence of findings reached nearly 100% at the highest pain levels, especially for bursitis, tendinitis, and meniscal lesions.

D. Analysis by age

Significant differences were observed in all ultrasound variables evaluated ($p=0.001$). Bursitis was more frequent in patients over 50 years (72.7%) and in the 41–50 age group (59.8%), compared with those aged 30–40 years (10%). Synovitis was absent in patients under 40 years, but increased to 6.6% in the 41–50 group and 13.6% in those over 50 years. Tendinitis showed a similar pattern, with low frequency in patients under 40 years (3.6%) and higher prevalence in the 41–50 (18%) and over 50 groups (42.9%). Meniscal lesions were identified in 4.3% of patients aged 30–40 years, increasing to 20.5% in those aged 41–50 and 37.7% in those over 50 years. Finally, cartilage changes were more frequent in older patients, present in 78.6% of those over 50 years and 61.5% of those aged 41–50, compared with only 7.1% in patients under 40 years.

E. Analysis by body mass index (BMI)

Significant differences were observed in all ultrasound variables evaluated. Bursitis was more frequent in patients with obesity (69.6%) and overweight (46.4%) compared with those with normal weight (38.7%; $p=0.004$). Synovitis showed a progressive increase, present in only 1.6% of patients with normal weight, increasing to 5.5% in overweight and up to 23.9% in obesity ($p=0.001$). Tendinitis was identified in 17.7% of patients with normal weight, 19.8% of those overweight, and 45.7% of obese patients ($p=0.001$). Similarly, meniscal lesions were more frequent

in obesity (43.5%) and overweight (19.5%) compared with normal weight (14.5%; $p=0.001$). Finally, cartilage changes were observed in 73.9% of obese patients and 48.7% of overweight patients, compared with 35.5% in those with normal weight ($p=0.001$).

V. DISCUSIÓN

George AW studied inflammatory and structural abnormalities using ultrasound, finding synovitis in 40%, cartilage damage in 39.3%, and bursitis in 38.7%. In concordance, in our study the most frequent findings were cartilage changes (49%) and bursitis (44%), followed by tendinitis, meniscal lesions, and synovitis, confirming the relevance of these alterations in the adult population with knee pain.

Mohammad and Basha reported that the most frequent ultrasonographic findings associated with anterior knee pain were bursitis (38%), cartilage changes (20.6%), and subcutaneous edema (20%). Similarly, Cakir Kandemirli indicated that bursitis is the most common finding (22%), although he emphasized that cartilage involvement has little relation to pain due to the scarce presence of nerve fibers in this tissue. In contrast, in our study the ultrasound findings associated with pain were bursitis in 84.4%, cartilage changes in 80%, tendinitis in 39%, meniscal lesions in 37.9%, and synovitis in 12.3%, demonstrating a significant association between ultrasound alterations and the presence of pain.

Cakir Kandemirli also described that patients with ultrasound findings presented higher values on the VAS scale, with predominance of alterations in moderate and severe pain, suggesting a progressive pattern. Our results confirm this trend: patients with moderate and severe pain showed higher frequency of bursitis, cartilage changes, and tendinitis, reinforcing the dose–response relationship between pain intensity and magnitude of structural damage.

Regarding personal factors, Kandemirli did not find significant differences in age, sex, or BMI. However, in our study advanced age and excess weight were associated with higher prevalence of ultrasound findings. Patients over 50 years had risks up to 47 times greater of presenting cartilage changes, and obesity was related to higher frequency of synovitis, meniscal lesions, and cartilage changes. These results coincide with those described by Valerio D’Agostino, who reported an association between age and osteoarthritis, reinforcing the evidence that age and excess weight are determining factors in joint degeneration.

In terms of physical activity, Beachu found that vigorous and moderate activity has a protective effect against knee pain, while mild or absent activity is associated with higher prevalence of symptoms. Our findings are consistent: pain was present in 66% of those performing mild activity, in 7.7% of those practicing moderate activity, and was practically absent in those performing vigorous activity.

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Finally, Driban reported that load-bearing sports are associated with osteoarthritis, but also noted that regular physical activity and active work reduce the risk of lesion progression. In our study, sports practice and active work were associated with lower prevalence of pain and ultrasound findings, suggesting that adequate physical activity contributes to maintaining joint health and preventing progression of musculoskeletal disease.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrated that knee pain in adult patients aged 30 to 60 years is significantly associated with specific ultrasound findings, mainly cartilage changes, bursitis, tendinitis, meniscal lesions, and synovitis. Pain prevalence was high, with predominance of bilateral and moderate pain, reflecting the clinical importance of this condition in the studied population

A dose–response pattern was evidenced between pain intensity (VAS) and the frequency of ultrasound findings, reaching prevalences close to 100% in patients with severe pain. Risk analysis confirmed that an increase in VAS score translates into a higher probability of presenting structural alterations, with particularly elevated risks for meniscal lesions and tendinitis.

Sociodemographic and clinical variables showed that advanced age and obesity significantly increase the risk of ultrasound findings. On the other hand, vigorous and moderate physical activity were associated with lower prevalence of pain and ultrasound findings, suggesting a protective effect against joint degeneration.

Taken together, the results confirm the usefulness of ultrasound as a diagnostic tool to correlate clinical symptoms with structural alterations of the knee, and highlight the importance of considering modifiable factors such as physical activity in prevention and treatment strategies. These findings provide solid evidence for clinical practice and open the possibility of interventions aimed at reducing the burden of musculoskeletal disease in this population.

This pattern reinforces the usefulness of ultrasound as a diagnostic tool to correlate clinical symptoms with structural changes, especially in pathologies such as osteoarthritis, tendinopathies, and meniscal lesions.

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